

D5.1 Definition and handbook of the Facilitation Service

Project Title	Research Data Alliance facilitation of Targeted International working Groups for EOSC-related Research solutions
Project Acronym	RDA TIGER
Grant Agreement No	101094406
Instrument	HORIZON-INFRA-2022-EOSC-01
Topic	HORIZON-INFRA-2022-EOSC-01-04
Start Date of Project	1 January 2023
Duration of Project	36 months
Project Website	https://www.rd-alliance.org/rda-tiger

Dissemination Level

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	PU: Public
<input type="checkbox"/>	PP: Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission)
<input type="checkbox"/>	RE: Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission)
<input type="checkbox"/>	CO: Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission)

Work Package	WP5
Lead Author (Org)	Najla Rettberg (RDA)
Contributing Author(s) (Org)	Alex Delipalta, Ari Asmi
Due Date	30.6.23
Submitted Date	30.6.23
Version	1.0 DRAFT NOT YET APPROVED BY THE EUROPEAN COMMISSION
DOI	10.5281/zenodo.8096642

Versioning and contribution history

Version	Date	Authors	Notes
0.5	6.6.23	Najla Rettberg, Alex Delipalta	First draft
1:0	9.6.23	Ari Asmi	Added new sections, and quality control section
1:5	20.6.23	Connie Clare	Internal review
1:5	20.6.23	Ryan O'Connor	Internal review
2:0	22.6.23	Najla Rettberg, Alex Delipalta	Final draft for consortium comment

Disclaimer

RDA TIGER has received funding from the European Commission’s HORIZON Coordination and Support programme under the Grant Agreement no. 101094406. The content of this document does not represent the opinion of the European Commission, and the European Commission is not responsible for any use that might be made of such content.

Abbreviations and Acronyms

BoF	Birds of a Feather
CODATA	Committee on Data of the International Science Council
DANS	Data Archiving and Networked Services
EOOSC	European Open Science Cloud
IG	Interest Groupresa
RDA	Research Data Alliance
TAB	RDA Technical Advisory Board (TAB)
WG	Working Group

Executive Summary

The Facilitation Service is the core of the RDA TIGER services. The RDA TIGER facilitator supports WGs from initiation to finalisation phase. This document outlines the Facilitation Service, the role of the facilitator, and sets out the stages of the Working Groups (WG) that the facilitator should oversee. It also highlights the links to the other support mechanisms that will be made available to the RDA WGs.

This deliverable is intended as an internal guidance document and will be complemented by two more updates in further deliverables (D5.2 and D5.3) which will evaluate and optimise the service based on service quality feedback from WP6.

Table of contents

Executive Summary	3
1. Context and Background	5
2. The Facilitation Service	5
2.1 Definition of WG stages within the RDA TIGER service platform	5
2.2 Service tracking	6
2.2.1. Quality indicators and follow up	6
2.3 The Role of the facilitator	7
3. Facilitation Stages	8
3.1 Overview of the facilitation lifecycle	8
3.2 F1: Partner Engagement	13
3.3 F2 WG Work Plan Creation	13
3.4 F3 Facilitation and WG Service Support	16
4. RDA TIGER Pilot stage: Lessons Learned	20
5. Conclusion and next steps	21
Appendix 1	22
[TEMPLATE] Service agreement for Facilitation of RDA TIGER supported working group	22
Purpose	22
What does a RDA TIGER facilitator do?	22
What does a RDA TIGER facilitator not do?	23
What are the WG co-chairs' responsibilities?	23

1. Context and Background

The RDA Working Groups (WGs) have proven to be a successful vehicle to deliver international community-led, concrete data-sharing Outputs and Recommendations. There are currently 47 active WGs listed on the RDA website¹. A clear process is in place for the operation and management of the WGs at various different stages of their life-cycle, overseen by the RDA Secretariat.² The RDA TIGER project complements these activities through the development and provision of a series of support services for new and existing RDA WGs, with the ultimate goal of producing high-quality RDA community Outputs that contribute to the international open science landscape.

The work of RDA is supported by the external RDA TIGER Selection Committee who oversee the allocation of resources (both service and financial support) to the WGs.

2. The Facilitation Service

The aim of the Facilitation Service in RDA TIGER is to give structured and hands-on support to RDA WGs. The RDA Foundation has not had formal WG facilitators in place to date; until now the organisation has relied on the RDA Secretariat staff for tasks requiring liaison with the Technical Advisory Board (TAB). This new role of WG facilitator plays a key part in the activities of RDA TIGER in terms of enabling the best results from the Groups from inception and during the work period, while allowing them to maintain focus on the ‘bottom up’ spirit and approach in their efforts to address data challenges.

2.1 Definition of WG stages within the RDA TIGER service platform

The RDA TIGER project has identified three general stages of the RDA WG life cycle. For clarity, graph 1 draws a parallel between what the project (and by extension this document) refers to as ‘stages’ and the official stages of the RDA WG life cycle:

Figure 1. RDA WG vs RDA TIGER life cycle stages

¹ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/working-groups> (to date, WP5 is using this page as the definitive source for the WGs)

² <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/creating-and-managing-rda-groups/creating-or-joining-rda-working-group.html>

It should be noted that RDA WGs maintaining deliverables (i.e., Maintenance Groups) will not be considered for service support within RDA TIGER. These groups will be eligible to apply for cascading grants, but, as per RDA rules for closing out WGs, any “new version or significant update of the recommendation, or to tackle additional work to e.g. cover more use cases” will require a new WG to be formed³. In these cases, the new WG can be considered for service support under the RDA TIGER project, subject to the established application process.

2.2 Service tracking

To ensure the RDA TIGER team delivers a high quality, professional and valuable service to the RDA community, a project management tool (Asana) is being utilised to track and manage all services and their associated tasks. The facilitator (described in section 2.4) is responsible for the creation and maintenance of projects (each new WG that receives support from RDA TIGER is set up as its own ‘project’ in Asana), as well as tracking all services for each group, ensuring the service tasks are delivered timely and professionally. A project template has been created, outlining all services and their associated tasks; this can be used each time a new WG is onboarded to the RDA TIGER service platform.

2.2.1. Quality indicators and follow up

The Facilitation Service can be categorised (as in D6.2) as a ‘person processing service’, with the primary target audience being WG members themselves in addition to users of potential WG outputs. Quality indicators are based on immediate feedback from WG members on the Facilitation Services using the standard RDA TIGER feedback mechanisms, mentioned below. In particular, the Facilitation Service uses the following feedback mechanisms:

1. **RDA TIGER Facilitation Service feedback survey.** This survey is shared with working group members (via a link) on completion of the stages of the Facilitation Service. Survey responses are collected in WP6, via a direct email to the RDA TIGER project coordinator, and the results periodically evaluated by WP6 for quality improvement, and the names of those sending feedback will remain anonymous. The results of the survey comprise both hard and soft quality indicators (as described in D6.2).
2. **RDA TIGER Facilitation Service feedback email.** An email account will be set up for feedback both to solicit feedback and to send feedback. These qualitative indicators are collected in WP6 and communicated to the WP5 team.
3. **Provider feedback.** The facilitator provides their feedback on the description, delivery and definition of the Facilitation Services. This feedback is collected internally in WP5, and discussed in the WP5 meetings.
4. **Hard quality indicators collected in WP6 and WP5.** These include more quantitative responses and are more connected to the Facilitation Service delivery and cost/benefit analyses. For RDA TIGER WP5, the most important internal KPIs related to the service delivery are:
 - a) Number of WGs supported by WP5;

³ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/creating-and-managing-rda-groups/creating-or-joining-rda-working-group.html>

- b) Number of virtual meetings organised;
- c) Number of physical meetings organised;
- d) Number of WG outputs finalised;
- e) Number of WG case statements supported;
- f) Number of people participating in the WG sessions.

These KPIs are collected internally in WP5 and reported to WP6.

2.3 The Role of the facilitator

RDA TIGER facilitators are members of the project consortium. Facilitators are assigned to WGs based on WG selection and approval for facilitation support by the Selection Committee, and the facilitator profile and area of expertise. Each WG that receives RDA TIGER support will be assigned one facilitator. The RDA Association currently employs one full-time facilitator, who is expected to manage and conduct the majority of facilitation tasks.

The role of facilitator will be varied, and the associated tasks will develop and evolve over time, in coordination with the activities of WP6. The service quality processes (developed as a sub-task in WP6) will ensure that the facilitator role is refined based on ongoing input and feedback as the project progresses.

The Facilitation Service can be divided into distinct stages, aligning with WG life cycle stages. Each Facilitation Service stage encompasses a number of steps aimed at supporting WGs with particular tasks and processes corresponding to the WG life cycle stage. Graph 2 depicts the Facilitation Services (referred to as 'F' services) in the wider RDA TIGER service platform context.

Figure 2. RDA TIGER services. Facilitation services ('F' services in blue).

The following principles provide a general guide to the facilitator's work:

- **Facilitate, not lead:** It is crucial that RDA WGs maintain their bottom-up, grassroots structure, with the co-chairs in place to engage and lead the WG. The facilitator will play a supporting role to assist and advise groups but is not expected to lead or make decisions about content.
- **Set boundaries:** The facilitator will set clear boundaries early on in the WG with the co-chairs regarding tasks within scope of the Facilitation Service provision.

3. Facilitation Stages

3.1 Overview of the facilitation lifecycle

The RDA WG life cycle (see also [section 2.1](#) above) forms the basis for how the facilitation life cycle is structured, planned and executed. Graph 3 depicts the WG lifecycle alongside the relevant RDA TIGER services.

Figure 3: RDA WG lifecycle in relation to the RDA TIGER services.

Table 1 provides more detail on the four facilitation stages identified by the RDA TIGER project.

Table 1. Facilitation Stages

Facilitation Service Stage		Description of facilitator tasks and activities	Concrete outputs for supported WGs
F1	Partner Engagement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Liaising with the RDA TIGER Selection Committee to identify the successful WGs who apply for service support. • Making suggestions for the WG membership (new groups), in coordination with the RDA TIGER Landscape service. • The facilitator will attend the RDA TIGER Selection Committee meetings to identify the successful WGs who apply for service support. • The facilitator will make suggestions for the WG membership, in coordination with the RDA TIGER Landscape service. 	Selection of the co-chairs, initial population of the RDA WG.
F2	Work Plan Creation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Discusses initial ideas for scope and objectives of the WG with co-chairs. • Discusses work plan, timelines, and responsibilities. • Creating the RDA TIGER support package following 	WG Case Statement WG work plan production

		<p>consultations with WG Group co-chairs.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Providing clear advice on what support the group can receive from the RDA TIGER Facilitation Service. ● The facilitator will take the lead in forming the RDA TIGER support package following consultations with WG co-chairs. WGs are required to present a work plan as part of their case statement and there will be overlap with the RDA TIGER facilitation workplan. 	
F3	Facilitation Service Support	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Coordinating group activities to keep them well-defined and in-scope. ● Providing support for running of meetings. ● Ensuring that all RDA processes and rules are followed by WG members. ● Providing advice on upcoming plenaries. ● Highlighting where RDA TIGER services resources may be available and signposting the WG co-chairs to the relevant application processes, providing guidance as necessary. 	WG adheres to its workplan.

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The facilitator will work with the supported WGs during their working period to keep them well-defined and in-scope. • The facilitator will highlight where RDA TIGER services resources may be available and will signpost the WG co-chairs to the relevant application processes, providing guidance as necessary. • The facilitator should make sure that all relevant RDA processes and rules are followed. 	
F4	WG Finalisation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Providing assistance with finalisation and delivery of Outputs • Connecting RDA TIGER services such as communications and landscape and Output services. • In addition to the points in F3, the facilitator will ensure co-chairs are aware of resources available to them (for example the Communications Service and the Outputs Service), as well as all processes for finalising and delivering the planned 	<p>WG produces draft and final Recommendation.</p> <p>WG Recommendation is adopted and implemented by relevant groups or organisations.</p>

		Outputs or Recommendations.	
--	--	-----------------------------	--

3.2 F1: Partner Engagement

Stage F1 (‘Partner Engagement’) describes the start of the process and initial arrangements between the RDA TIGER facilitator and the WG. While this stage applies broadly to all supported WGs, regardless of their individual life cycle stage (i.e, WGs at mid- or late-stage of their cycle will require planning activities in coordination with the facilitator), particular attention will be given to new WGs as they have additional requirements with regards to establishing and building membership, drafting their case statement, and refining their scope and objectives.

F.1.1. Assigning the facilitator

This assignment is done after acceptance of the `WG by the Selection Committee. As described above (Section 2.3), the Selection Committee assigns the facilitator on the basis of profile, area of expertise and availability/capacity.

F.1.2. Inform WG members about the provided services and their limitations

The facilitator sends the template of services to initial members of the WG so they are aware of the scope of the TIGER support services. The Landscape service should provide a landscape report where requested.

During this stage, the facilitator coordinates with the following RDA TIGER Services:

- **S1 | Onboarding:** The facilitator will support WGs in their starting phase. In addition to informing the WG of TIGER support services, the facilitator will ensure the WG conforms with RDA TIGER impact and participation requirements. At this stage, the facilitator seeks approval from the project coordinator (submitter of the RDA TIGER application) to onboard the WG to the Facilitation Service platform. This onboarding stage applies to all WGs regardless of their lifecycle stage.

3.3 F2 WG Work Plan Creation

Identifying the problem or challenge is essential to starting a WG. Before a WG can be formed and endorsed, a series of actions must take place to ensure it develops and progresses with an appropriate idea, scope and objective. It may take months or even years to concoct, develop and propose a suitable idea for a WG. Sometimes WGs emerge organically as an outcome of a Birds of a Feather Plenary session (BoF), from discussions within Interest Group (IG) meetings, or as continuations of work done by previous WGs. In some cases, ideas for WGs emerge in rapid response to salient data sharing challenges, such as COVID-19. Irrespective of how an idea for a WG emerges within the RDA community, preliminary work must be undertaken to develop the idea and devise a work plan.

A WG case statement needs realistic and achievable objectives with concrete deliverables, and a volunteer membership that is committed to the work plan for the entire duration of the WG. For this reason, WG case statements are rigorously reviewed by RDA's Technical Advisory Board (TAB).

The WG case statement is created with the WG members, including clear definitions of the roles and responsibilities of members, and a timeline of internal milestones and achievements. The facilitator will work with the WG members at this stage to question whether the case statement work plan is practical and will enable the WG to complete its activities within its 18-month lifespan. The facilitator will rely on the WG members to understand if their case statement is achievable. They can liaise with the Output service at this point to get advice on the best type/format, and how to make the Output FAIR, as described below (O1).

The case statement includes definitions and expected progression of internal monitoring metrics of the WG.

It should be emphasised that the responsibility of the facilitator throughout the various stages described above is to provide advice and guidance, not to handle the WG's specific tasks, such as selecting the co-chairs.

The sub-stages of this Facilitation service stage are described below.

F2.1. Help internal organisation of the WG - selection of chairs, clarifying the mission of the WG

The facilitator, in collaboration with co-chairs, collates and contacts a list of potential WG members. The facilitator will liaise with WG members and chairs to identify and refine the scope and objectives of the WG. The WG membership will be managed by the RDA web platform, ensuring GDPR is adhered to.

F2.2. Help draft case statement and submit it

The facilitator guides the co-chairs, providing advice as required, on how to draft the case statement, using the RDA case-statement template⁴. The co-chairs are responsible for drafting the statement, leveraging the knowledge and support of the facilitator. RDA has created various guidance materials which can be used to support the facilitator and WG⁵. Support provided by the facilitator may include text editing, collecting examples from other case statements and serving as liaison with relevant RDA bodies, primarily the TAB and Secretariat). The case statement will stay open for comment from all WG members for 2 weeks before submission to the TAB by the chairs. The facilitator will collect the response and help the chairs with any adjustments if needed.

The WG case statement is the first step in formally initiating a WG. All RDA WGs must submit a case statement in order to become an official WG. There will be no exceptions or special considerations for WGs supported by RDA TIGER.

⁴ <https://zenodo.org/record/7506212#.Y7bOEuzMJLk>

⁵ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/creating-and-managing-rda-groups/case-statement-development-and-review-process.html>

The case statement puts forward an intended ‘recommendation’. The recommendation should, according to RDA, ‘strive for focused effort and tangible process’⁶.

F2.3. Create a work plan for the WG

Using a template created in coordination with WP2 by the Communications Service, the facilitator drafts an initial work plan which is approved by the WG. It should be stressed that the RDA TIGER work plan is not the same as the WG work plan, which is part of the Case Statement and the formal RDA WG creation process. Rather, the RDA TIGER work plan intends to outline all services and actions planned and implemented by RDA TIGER during the lifetime of the project.

Once approved the facilitator then documents the work plan steps in Asana (see section 2.3 on Service Tracking) and establishes the timeline and milestones. The work plan incorporates the WG’s communication plan, as defined in coordination with the Communications Services.

F2.4. Help to submit a support application (if needed) for 3rd party services and other available grants

Based on the available services on offer via the Open Call process, the facilitator discusses the list of possible services with the WG and an application is made to the Selection Committee.

F2.5. Create a Service Agreement for Facilitation with the WG chairs

This step outlines and agrees expectations regarding the facilitator’s contribution, effort and specific support tasks provided to the WG. A contract outlining the specific service provision over the life-time of the WG will be drawn, including clear definitions of the roles and responsibilities of the facilitator and chairs. This template can be found in Appendix 1 below.

F2 ‘Work Plan Creation’ also coordinates with the following support services:

F2 Work plan Creation coordinates with the following services:

- **A1 | Initial landscape analysis:** This analysis service ensures that there is no duplication of effort both within the partner networks (RDA, CODATA, DANS, Netherlands eScience Centre) and in the wider landscape with regards to the planned activities on the subject matter of the WG. The analysis will map similar initiatives or potential interested parties, targeting national, EOSC, European and international initiatives. This service utilises the outputs and contacts compiled by WP3 and the overall Landscape Service, while also directly networking with WG participants and other consortium contacts. The associated tasks include desk research, interviews and direct communications to potentially relevant initiatives. This service stage applies to new WGs.
- **C1 | Idea dissemination:** The facilitator will work with the Communications Lead to disseminate news about new WGs, and build WG membership and engagement. The

⁶<https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/creating-and-managing-rda-groups/creating-or-joining-rda-working-group.html>

facilitator will recruit new WG members by sending an introductory email to those identified as potential members, detailing important information about the WG and how to get involved. The facilitator will draft the email and the Communications Service will proof-read it, and identify relevant channels for its dissemination. The Selection Committee may also suggest potential WG members and co-chairs. This stage applies to new WGs.

- **O1 | Output definition:** Working Group outputs must be clearly defined during the Work Plan Creation stage. Service O1 can support this endeavour, and the specifics will be incorporated into the work plan, including:
 - (i) the initial definition of the output scope;
 - (ii) potential output adopters/users;
 - (iii),
 - (iii) any required support actions (e.g. for standardisation of outputs); and,
 - (iv) output maintenance and sustainability requirements.

This stage applies to new WGs.

- **S2 | Support Needs and Planning & Approval:** The facilitator evaluates the needs of WGs for external support services based on its work plan. This service includes internal RDA TIGER organisational steps, such as;
 - (i) an assessment of needs for 3rd party support and/or adoption grants, and the nomination of a WG representative on the selection committee for evaluation, of such grants;
 - (ii) a definition of and budget for potential consultant services needed, and;
 - (iii) the number and recipient of travel grants provided in the WG.

Project board approval for these external services will be required. This service stage applies to all supported WGs regardless of their lifecycle stage. This stage also refers to the provision of practical support in getting WG approval within the RDA processes and mechanisms. It includes helping to formulate the case statement, direct support to adjust the statement in the case of additional clarifications, etc. This service stage applies to WGs starting out.

3.4 F3 Facilitation and WG Service Support

This service stage refers to the types of support that can be provided to the WGs during the main working period of the WG. This is defined as the period after the case statement has been approved, and before the final months leading up to Output finalisation and completion of the WG.

The following stages of the service are described below.

F3.1 Physical meeting organisation

Physical meetings will primarily take place at the RDA Plenary meetings, which are held twice a year. The support tasks in this stage will primarily focus on planning ahead of time with the WG, ensuring Plenary WG calls of session applications are on time, and providing support with writing and submitting the session application for the meeting. Once a session is accepted by the TAB and Secretariat, the facilitator will support the chairs with the session scheduling process led by the RDA Secretariat and will provide general support with planning the session as needed. The facilitator will liaise with the Communications Service for the promotion of the session, in an effort to increase Group membership and attract attendees. The facilitator can also suggest any specific facilitation methods and actions to be used during the meeting (e.g., group work, on-site surveys, panels, etc.).

Events other than the Plenary may also be supported on demand (virtual or face to face, internal or external facing (depending on facilitator availability)). The facilitator will assist with venue arrangements, programme development and publication on the RDA website, and will liaise with the Communications Service for the promotion of the event. If there is financial support needed for the venue (meeting facilities, catering, etc.) the group can apply for an RDA TIGER open call on this basis. Based on the Landscape service, targeted invitation of event participants/attendees may be necessary. Event Registration services can also be provided for example, setting up an event landing/registration page. During the meeting, the facilitator will organise note taking (i.e., ensure note-taking duties are assigned), create additional facilitation actions (if agreed beforehand) and if necessary, help with the meeting practicalities.

F3.2 Virtual meeting organisation, facilitation and documentation

Before virtual meetings the facilitator will organise relevant practicalities of the meetings (links, calendar invites, etc.), and work with the co-chairs to prepare the agenda and action items of the meetings. Meeting participants will be reminded of the RDA's guiding principles, code of conduct⁷ and AI tool usage guidance⁸. The facilitator will also maintain the event registration pages if needed. The virtual meeting support can also include targeted outreach and individual invites, as well as general outreach about the meeting; this can be done in collaboration with the Communications Service.

WGs meet as regularly as they need, according to their plan. The facilitator can agree with the group who will take the minutes (this will not necessarily be the facilitator) and share the necessary documentation beforehand. The facilitator can act as additional support during the virtual meeting by handling platform issues, providing technical support, assisting with co-chairs where needed, and suggesting next steps/actions. Assistance may also include use of additional tools (surveys, polls, etc.) during the meeting.

F3.3. Facilitating support request preparation

The facilitator will help the WG to prepare (additional) grant support requests to the Selection Committee, for example they may want an adoption grant or help with promotion of outputs. This will involve informing WGs on the potential types of support (for example meeting facilitation, report

⁷ <https://rd-alliance.org/rd-code-conduct-and-how-report-breach>

⁸ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/rd-guidance-ai-tools-usage>

writing, expert consultancy), providing guidance on how to apply for them and helping with the applications.

F3.4. Internal management of the WG within the RDA TIGER

The facilitator is responsible for all internal coordination actions for the Groups that have been assigned to them. This means ensuring processes are followed, tracked and documented on Asana, liaising with all Services as needed, tracking and managing effort spent on Services, and escalating any potential issues and risks to the RDA TIGER Project Coordinator as needed.

F3 works in coordination with the following services:

- **A2 | WG Landscape monitoring:** Activities in this service stage continue on from A1 (see section 3.2 above) by providing periodic updates to the Groups based on developments in the field and relevant findings from the overall Landscape and Engagement Service (WP3). This service stage applies to all stages of the WGs development.
- **C2 | Internal and external WG Communications.** This service manages internal WG communication services, such as WG web page maintenance, internal contact information management, periodic internal bulletins (email lists), and communication tools management and provision (Slack, etc). External dissemination and communication services include periodic progress updates disseminated via the website and mailing lists, management of external communication lists related to a WG, dissemination in preparation for RDA Plenaries and International Data Week meetings (i.e., session promotion), in addition to effective dissemination of progress updates to interested bodies identified in A1 and A2 services. This service stage applies to WGs in the Work Period lifecycle stage.
- **S3 | Direct Management Support:** This service manages the external 3rd party calls for the WG, including preparation of the call text and evaluation and awarding of the grants, together with the WG and Selection Committee (S7, augmented by a WG member for specialist information). The task includes management of the calls (authoring, publication), handling legal and financial issues related to calls, as well as communications tasks and activities related to publications of the calls. The task also includes provision of travel support for the WG members, and specification and hiring of any subcontracted consultant services for WG tasks and activities. This service stage applies to WGs in the Work Period lifecycle stage.

3.4 F4: WG Finalisation Support Services

One of the most challenging stages of the WG is ensuring that it delivers its planned outputs and/or Recommendations. The co-chairs have to maintain engagement from all WG members to ensure the work is carried out to a high-standard and to plan.

The facilitator will play a critical role at this stage and ensure the following last-mile support is provided:

F4.1 Last mile support and facilitation

The facilitator will help the WG in finalisation of their Outputs (note that the facilitator provides guidance and is not responsible for writing the Outputs themselves). This support can refer to the practical organisation of work, reminding of tasks, maintaining internal communications, document control (access, responding to comments), editing documents, and assigning tasks (together with Chairs). This activity also includes the facilitation of additional support actions (as in F3.4).

This sub-service includes also the support for actual finalisation of the WG, guidance to the WG members on the RDA WG closure, future options (e.g., via RDA WG maintenance mode), and collect the feedback on the WG operations.

F4.2 Facilitating output maintenance activities

The facilitator will inform the WG on the potential Output services from WP4 and help the integration of other Services.

F4 works in coordination with the following services:

- **C3 | Dissemination of outputs:** WG-Output specific targeted dissemination of the WG outputs, including the creation and running of social media campaigns, website posts and news item, the organisation of bespoke, targeted events, and through the use of other direct mechanisms (dissemination materials, podcasts) aiming to increase the awareness of the WG output in the relevant target groups. These target communities are defined in the service O1 and can be further developed based on the progress from services O2 and O3 for this WG output.
- **O3 | Guidance for Policy outputs:** This helpdesk service provides guidance to WGs that develop policies in the area of research data in the broad sense, including Open and FAIR data policies. At the domain level, national level and in the EOSC context this kind of policy is being formulated and revised, e.g., by EOSC Association Task Forces. The helpdesk helps RDA WGs to check how their (planned or draft) policy document fits into the wider policy landscape. Starting from a set of key data policies within EOSC, the helpdesk can point WGs to existing policies for inspiration or alignment. This may include a moderate level of desk research within EOSC and national European data-related policies; domain-specific policies will probably be out of scope. Its work is demand-driven and responds to policy-related questions from WGs. The helpdesk is fed by the landscape services in the project, which will also lead to updates of the set of key data policies. The helpdesk will develop a lightweight feedback form.
- **O4 | Guidance for Standardisation:** RDA working groups face a significant challenge in scanning the EOSC landscape, standards, and requirements as an input to working group

activities, and likewise, ensuring that their recommendations and outputs are aligned with and implementable in the context of EOSC. An expert service is provided to bridge the gap and maintain guidelines, design considerations, and specifications applicable. The service integrates with the platform for output publication and maintenance (1.2.4)

- **O5 | Output Sustainability and Maintenance** provided via the RDA Maintenance platform development in WP4.
- **S4 | Adoption Support:** This service provides optional adoption grants to test the WG outputs in real-world environments. These grants are treated like third party grants and will need to be applied for separately.

4. RDA TIGER Pilot stage: Lessons Learned

The RDA TIGER project runs on a Pilot phase during the first year of the project⁹. As a result of preliminary work which has taken place in the first five months of the project, the Facilitation, Communications and Landscape and Engagement teams have gathered valuable lessons from the Pilot Groups:

- **Capacity and measuring the work:** There is a clear need to track effort spent by the team on certain tasks. As the services are still new and, in many cases, either still under development or being refined, it is hard to quantify the appropriate time required for each service stage. The team will therefore record effort spent carefully, and in close collaboration with WP6, the services will be refined, dependencies will be identified, and activities will be optimised. This will also serve to inform any service offering developed by RDA to Groups beyond the end of the RDA TIGER project.
- **Expectation management:**
 - It has been observed from the Groups the team has interacted with during the Pilot stage that there were certain expectations from the RDA TIGER project with regards to the depth of the available support, in particular pertaining to financial support, such as travel grants. As set out in Appendix 2, the facilitator agreement should be given to the WG co-chairs as early as possible, and expectations should be managed and clarified from the start.
 - The facilitator should work closely with the WG and keep developing and refining the services, as these are still at a trial stage.
- **There is a need for a ‘Facilitation Handbook’:** Work on the WP6 RDA TIGER pilots so far has shown that first efforts in Facilitation need to be improved. For example, there should be a checklist when holding a first meeting (recording, ensuring someone makes a list of attendees, giving clear next steps and deadlines), and other such tools to streamline the process and make the workflow easier to replicate as more Groups take off.

⁹ See here for an overview of the pilots in RDA TIGER: <https://www.rd-alliance.org/rda-tiger#Pilot%20Groups>

5. Conclusion and next steps

The Facilitation Service is ready to be rolled out and all the theoretical steps have been carefully mapped out. The next step is to put the workflow into practice both with the pilots (WP6) and with the results of the first round for the Facilitation Call, which closed at the end of May 2023.

Working closely with WP6, it is essential that the Facilitation Service starts to gather input on running the Facilitation Service as early as possible from the Pilot groups. Some of these Groups have started mid-way through the WG lifecycle and can therefore give feedback on different stages of the WG at an early stage. RDA TIGER WP6 will receive the service quality feedback in a structured way (see D6.2 RDA TIGER ‘Service Quality Definitions¹⁰). In addition, the WP5 team, working with the facilitator, should be asking questions such as: is this Facilitation stage necessary, can it be merged with other services, and most crucially, gap-spotting in areas that simply are not possible to identify until the WGs start.

¹⁰ [10.5281/zenodo.8096659](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8096659)

Appendix 1

[TEMPLATE] Service agreement for Facilitation of RDA TIGER supported working group

Purpose

This document clarifies the role of the facilitator in the Working Group support actions carried out by the RDA TIGER project (Jan 2023 - Dec 2025).

What does a RDA TIGER facilitator do?

The role of the RDA TIGER facilitator is to help co-chairs to run the Working Group (WG) and to increase the effectiveness of the Working Group as a whole. In detail, the facilitator can:

- Act as an interface between the WG and the RDA TIGER services (communications, grant applications, output support, etc.);
- Act as an interface between the WG and the wider RDA organisation to guide the Group as needed in terms of navigating RDA, including acting as the interface with Secretariat and other governance bodies as needed (or signposting the WG towards the appropriate body for any issues that arise);
- Help with planning and defining the WG case statement, work plan, activities and outputs;
- Advise on the landscape of relevant groups and initiatives upon request, including creating connections to WP3 and RDA TAB if necessary;
- Support the keeping of a schedule of meetings and participant information for those meetings;
- Remind WG members of agreed tasks and deadlines;
- Help with meeting planning if required and where resources exist, for example, by preparing a virtual meeting platform, helping to source in-person meeting facilities if required, ensuring an agenda is prepared and agreed before the meeting, ensuring that note-taking duties are allocated to a WG member in advance of the meeting and/or other recording methods are used, and ensuring that the responsibility for the production of documents and notes is allocated in advance;
- Provide additional in-meeting help with, for example, additional facilitation tools (breakouts, noteboards, etc.), managing the virtual waiting room, helping the chairs and the WG members to concentrate on the intended WG outputs, ensuring that there are equal opportunities for the WG members to participate in discussions, time-keeping to an agreed agenda, alerting co-chairs to questions or feedback. However, these roles need to be agreed in detail and in advance with the WG co-chairs;
- Provide editorial support for the documents and outputs developed. They can direct the co-chairs to apply for additional resources from RDA TIGER if needed for these activities;
- Escalate to the RDA TIGER project coordinator in the case of unresponsive WG co-chairs or other obstructions to the performance of support of the orderly progress of the group.

What does a RDA TIGER facilitator not do?

The RDA TIGER facilitators are **not** intended to:

- Act as meeting secretaries. They can optionally take notes if this is needed and possible, but it is strongly preferred that note-taking is allocated to an existing co-chair or member of the WG due to their topic expertise and familiarity with the terminology of the WG area;
- Direct the WGs, or take responsibility for strategic choices about its focus or outputs;
- Assume responsibility for the delivery, timely or otherwise, of WG outputs;
- Be held responsible for the provision of meeting rooms, whether virtual or physical, or other facilities;
- Chair the sessions or the work, but are there instead to support the orderly progress of the WG;
- Be responsible for any task or activity, during or outside meetings, that has not been specifically agreed between co-chairs and the facilitator in advance;
- Be involved in resolution of conflict within the WG or between co-chairs. Where this situation occurs, the facilitator may request to the RDA TIGER Coordinator to withdraw from support activity for the WG.

What are the WG co-chairs' responsibilities?

WG co-chairs are critical to the success of the facilitation relationship. This section sets out some guidance for co-chairs to help ensure the facilitation work has the best chance of success.

- The presence of a facilitator from the RDA TIGER project does not preclude the co-chairs from retaining responsibility for their existing roles. The facilitation work is focused on support of these activities to foster an orderly progress of the WG towards timely delivery of well-defined and appropriate outputs suitable for wider adoption within and beyond the RDA community;
- WG co-chairs and facilitators should approach this work as trusted and trustworthy colleagues collaborating on an equal footing; there is no line management relationship implied in the facilitation agreement;
- All parties should abide by the RDA Code of Conduct¹¹ in dealing with each other as well as in WG meetings;
- WG co-chairs and facilitators should ensure that there is a full and timely flow of information between the parties. Co-chairs should not assume the facilitator will perform any particular duty during or outside WG meetings without clear agreement in advance;
- Co-chairs are free to formulate any reasonable request relevant to the work of the WG to the facilitator. Facilitators are free to refuse requests for any activity or responsibility that they are unable to perform or unwilling to carry out on the grounds of resource, capacity or relevance to the scope of the WG;
- Facilitators should make it clear when the RDA TIGER services end; in most cases, this will be at the end of the RDA TIGER project in December 2025, regardless of the WG lifecycle stage and whether WG activity will carry on beyond the end of RDA TIGER.

¹¹ <https://rd-alliance.org/rda-code-conduct-and-how-report-breach>

- Meeting duties and output development and delivery remain ultimately the responsibility of the WG co-chairs; requests for assistance towards these activities must be clearly provided with reasonable notice ahead of time to the facilitator. It should be recognised that the facilitator may have a number of WGs to support and so timelines must allow for the facilitator to balance competing demands on their time and resources.

